

The background of the slide is a vibrant, colorful landscape. The top half shows a rocky coastline with patches of blue, purple, and red, possibly representing a reef or a specific type of rock formation. The bottom half shows a sandy beach with a person in a red shirt walking towards the water, carrying a surfboard. A large, semi-transparent purple oval is overlaid on the left side of the image, containing the text.

Transformation Action Workshop III

Milestone 7

Spatial Planning Process – Instrumental Perspectives

Technical References

Project Acronym	BioValue
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Executive Summary

Despite international and European policies in place to halt biodiversity loss, the effect of multi-level, and multi-sector, direct and indirect drivers of change contribute to continuing negative trends. As biodiversity is impacted by many different sectors, the main challenge consists in balancing a wide range of interests and value systems across different political levels, negotiating different interests while ultimately seeking to improve, or at least maintain, biodiversity.

The main goal of BioValue is to safeguard and enhance biodiversity through transformative change in spatial policymaking, planning practices and infrastructure development, upscaling opportunities for valuing biodiversity in support of EU strategic actions on biodiversity, particularly the EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030. To address this, BioValue adopts three complementary instrumental perspectives relevant to spatial planning processes: spatial planning and management instruments (SP&MI), environmental assessment instruments (EAI), and economic and financial instruments (E&FI).

The instrumental perspectives will support the structuring of the research in three case studies (in Portugal, Italy, and Germany) to explore and experiment BioValue research frameworks with stakeholders in action. The case studies will work as arenas for transformation (arenas₄transf), as 'experimental' areas of the capacity of the three instruments to create transformative change for biodiversity value enhancement. These cases represent distinct spatial planning systems and cultures, as well as for scale and biodiversity-related situations.

This report **delivers the results of the 3rd Transformation Action Workshop** (TAW III) which aimed to understand the integration of the three instrumental perspectives in the Arenas spatial planning processes and collectively identify possible transformative pathways.

The TAWs are a series of spaces of collective thinking to co-create action-oriented knowledge and transformative pathways throughout the arenas₄transf processes. Specific objectives of the TAWs are:

- i. Support the structure of the transformation processes of the arenas₄transf
- ii. Formulate needs and opportunities
- iii. Help co-creation and discussion among the arenas₄transf
- iv. Facilitate knowledge brokerage between the arenas₄transf
- v. Advance improvements for transformation of joint application of the three instrumental perspectives

One more TAW is expected to occur in month 30 (in Portugal).

The TAW III report constitutes BioValue Milestone 7 and it is a project public resource.

Transformation Action Workshop III

Spatial Planning Process – Instrumental
Perspectives

TAW III Objectives

Transformation Action Workshop III

Part I - May 2024 (month 23)

Part II - June 2024 (month 24 - online session)

Understand the integration of the three instrumental perspectives in the Arenas spatial planning processes

Specific objectives:

- Explore what can be the contributions of the instrumental perspectives to the Arenas spatial planning processes - explore the 'how to' based on the Arena's expectations and on the need for some practical clarifications.
- Identify, collectively, possible transformative pathways.

TAW III: Structure of the workshop

Duration: 2h30

Activities:

- 1: Contributions of the instrumental perspectives to the Arenas (25min each round, 3 rounds) ~ 1h05
(10 minutes rest)
- 2: Sharing results (plenary) (arenas) ~ 30min (10 minutes per Arena)

TAW III: Structure of the workshop

Duration: 50min

Activities:

- 1: Groups discussion, per Arena, to reflect on the integration of the three instrumental perspectives (40min)
- 3: Plenary wrap-up (10min)

TAW III: Activities

Part I

May 2024 (month 23)

Activity 1

Contributions of the instrumental perspectives to the Arenas

1. Each Arena must briefly explain the main aspects of the Arena and needs in relation to the Work Package in the Table
 2. The Work Package share the practical tips with the Arenas
3. Together in group, discuss the 'how to' based on the Arena's expectations and on the need for some practical clarifications

Part II

June 2024 (online)

Activity 2 – zoom meeting

Compilation of Results – Reflection on the integration of the instruments

1. Collectively discuss on, for the Arena's spatial planning process and based on the results of TAW III part I.

Activity 3 – zoom meeting

Sharing results

1. One representative of the Arena share the results with all the group (10 minutes per Arena)

TAW III: Support material

Part I

May 2024 (month 23)

- Summary of previous TAWs results
- Arena's Agendas
- Work Packages Practical Tips
- Blank A1 sheet
- Arena's Expectations
- Colour Pens
- Post-its

Part II

June 2024 (month 24 - online)

- Summary of previous TAW III part I results

Transformation Action Workshop I&II

Previous findings

Transformation Action Workshop I & II – Main Results

(month 9 and 15)

Overall findings:

- **Awareness:** the need to promote public (including landowners) and institutional awareness and potentiate human-nature interactions/relationships – this can be done by support schemes to promote a societal recognition of the possible uses of valued biodiversity.
- **Capacitation:** increase capacity building and knowledge brokerage programmes on biodiversity and natural assets (adoption of appreciative approaches for recognition and valuing of...).
- **Policy integration:** promote and develop inter-institutional working programmes for policy integration through cross-sectoral collaboration and boundary-spanning mechanisms).
- **Perceptions:** rethink land –use, -ownership, -management through promoting positive approaches to recognize value in all its dimensions (economic, social and natural).

Transformation Action Workshop I – Main Results

(month 9)

BioValue team TAW I:

- **Perceptions:** importance of understanding the different perceptions at stake, working towards change in promoting shared thinking about the importance of biodiversity for territorial development and spatial planning systems.
- **Regulations:** current regulations are restrictive in nature and may not be expressing, in a positive way, different policy options for spatial transformation that cope with biodiversity and nature. There is the need to overcome current practices of 'working in silos' and to promote cross-sectoral approaches.
- **Ownership:** Is important to shift from thinking of biodiversity and natural capital as restrictive in a way for policymakers/landowners to take ownership of their territories and thus recognize the possible uses of valued biodiversity.
- **Governance:** governance systems need to promote relational approaches to promote cooperation and collaboration among different decision-making levels.
- **Awareness:** more needs to be done to raise awareness on biodiversity and nature to, in a positive and informed way, consider/integrate biodiversity value in spatial planning policies and more local practices.
- **Valuation:** overall recognition that 'green does not have an economic value' and does not 'represent development', and the importance of overcoming current perceptions to recognize value in all of its dimensions (economic, social and natural).

Transformation Action Workshop I – Main Results

(month 9)

Local TAWs:

Trento:

- Excessive artificiality
- Creation of green corridors
- Promote proximity with nature (potentiate human-nature relationships)
- Need for integrated management approaches
- Need for control of polluting activities and prevention of pollution
- Lack of knowledge

Mafra:

- Increase the willingness of policy-makers/decision-makers/local actors
- Raise awareness – explicit consequences/impacts
- Education / capacity-building of a sectoral entities on biodiversity and natural values
- Blue and green areas. Preserve the “green” – adopt an ecosystems approach
- Water as a strategic asset.
- Agrifood systems

Meck-Pomm:

- Rewetting for climate protection - include climate protection as a category in the list of priority areas
- Lack of human resources in administrative bodies – need for adaptation of institutional structures of the planning system
- Integration of different policies proofs difficult on the ground
- Small scale land ownership and subsidies for farming, biodiversity conservation conflicts – Intersectoral challenges

Transformation Action Workshop II – Main Results

(month 15)

BioValue team TAW I:

- **Ambition 1:**

(Meck-Pomm)

- Adaptation of the institutional spatial planning systems.
- Local, regional, federal needs and expectations.
- Synergies between climate change protection and biodiversity in combination with climate change mitigation.

- **Ambition 3:**

(Mafra)

- Basic need in the planning process – to shift attention to ecosystem services.
- System of transfer of development rights: to limit urban sprawl and compensate market inequalities.
- Satisfy necessities of poorer sectors of society.
- Manage sector inequalities – e.g., with intersectoral compensation mechanisms.
- Financial schemes for private agriculture to value biodiversity: e.g., non-intensive eco-compatible agricultural production.
- Cooperative approaches.

(Trento)

- Promote socio-economic cohesion.
- Unified and shared vision on *the entire*.
- Green spaces as places for integration, places for 'meeting' and interaction.
- Finding balance between regeneration of areas (suburbs) and gentrification of increasing house prices.
- Accessibility to the river in all its dimensions.

Transformation Action Workshop II – Main Results

(month 15)

Ambition 1: spatial planning safeguards, restores, allows recovery and enhances biodiversity.

Local TAWs - Trento:

CANYON

KEY WORDS: PROTECTED AREAS AND BIO CORRIDORS ; PROACTIVELY ENHANCE BIODIVERSITY ; CONNECTIONS WITH NATURE ; STIMULATE POSITIVE SOCIAL INTERACTION ; SECURITY ; ECOSYSTEM SERVICE ; RESTRICT OR PRESCRIBE USE

- Establishing a recognized Natural park in the “Ponte Alto” area
- Contamination and pollution from illegal dumping (active: area monitoring and local policing; passive: citizens use of area as Park to prevent misuse)
- Water use policy - preventing total drought due to irrigation of upfield streams
- Awareness - lack of local awareness and knowledge of local ecosystem (mapping local flora and fauna)
- Limit excessive recreational use (not transforming area into waterfront with heavy anthropization)

URBAN SEGMENT

KEY WORDS: URBAN GREEN & BLUE AREAS ; LOCAL BIODIVERSITY ; PROACTIVELY ENHANCE BIODIVERSITY ; BIO CORRIDORS ; ECOSYSTEM SERVICES ; WELL-BEING ; CONNECTION WITH NATURE ; STIMULATION OF POSITIVE SOCIAL INTERACTIONS

- Reduce artificiality of river Banks
- Limit aggressive maintenance of vegetation along the riverbed to allow habited enhancement (i.e. selective vegetation cutting)
- Intercept and prevent littering of riverbed
- Water quality is medium poor in the Urban context -> preventive measures to monitor water quality and an authorized inflows
- Water flow management: daily hydro peaking and drought throughout the seasons -> improving management to overcome flow inconsistency
- Green continuity - establishing a connection of urban green areas in order to limit fragmentation of same

DELTA

KEY WORDS: ECOSYSTEM SERVICES ; HEALTH IMPACTS ; WELL-BEING ; SECURITY

- Establishing a fluvial park on the Delta in relation to the Future Hospital -> Management in high risk zone (Adige + Fersina) -> positive impact on HealthCare for future patients as complementary therapy
- Reducing artificiality of Banks
- Water pollution control (periodic presence of foam on water)
- Ecological monotony - selective vegetation maintenance instead of aggressive one, two allow habitat settling
- Create morphological diversity to foster biodiversity
- Prevent excessive green loss with the hospital Project

Transformation Action Workshop II – Main Results

(month 15)

Local TAWs - Trento:

Ambition 2: spatial planning significantly contributes to balanced and responsible consumption and production (avoiding external social and environmental costs).

CANYON

KEY WORDS: BIODIVERSITY ; MIXED USE PLANNING

- Establishing biopark - artificial water basin used for local irrigation of agricultural Consulting and fisherman Association for recreational fishing -> integrate in the plan for naturalistic park and enhance for recreational use
- Water flow management: unauthorised water withdrawal upstream for irrigation purposes leads to seasonal droughts and ecosystem loss (valid also for urban and delta)

URBAN SEGMENT

KEY WORDS: URBAN FOOD PRODUCTION ; POLLINATORS ; BIODIVERSITY ; ALLOCATING AREAS AND INCENTIVES ; LESS FOOD IMPORTS

- Enhancing existing urban Orchards and integrating new ones in green areas planning along the River
- Integrating areas for fisherman association in design
- Enhancing river morphology and habitat to Foster fish population
- Vegetation management prevent habitat loss for pollinators (valid also for delta)

DELTA

KEY WORDS: REDUCE CONVERSION TO URBAN USE ; COMPACT CITIES; URBAN FOOD PRODUCTION ; POLLINATORS ; REDUCE LANDSCAPE FRAGMENTATION

- Preserving high quality agricultural land “le ghiaie” to limit excessive loss due to urbanization and new hospital location in the area (especially due to location of New Campus)
- Integrating Orchards in therapeutic programming of green areas of the hospital / campus

Transformation Action Workshop II – Main Results

(month 15)

Local TAWs - Mafra:

Transformation Action Workshop II – Main Results

(month 15)

Local TAWs - Mafra:

Scenario 1 (*desirable, sustainable*):

- Ambition 1:
 - Decrease in the creation of green and blue areas (e.g., due to social withdrawal).
 - More access to biodiversity information.
 - Increase in the regeneration of protected areas.
- Ambition 2:
 - Agricultural automation.
 - Land abandonment, segregation of the rural, concentration of economic activities.
 - Increase in the production due to technological developments.
 - Flexible institutional structures.

Scenario 4 (*plausible, probable*):

- Ambition 1:
 - Governmental rigidity in defining the 'where' of green and blue areas.
 - Control of uses in natural spaces.
 - Political cycles dictate investments.
- Ambition 2:
 - Dietary control by a consequent change in agricultural production.
 - Intensive and large-scale production.
 - Urban settlements well defined.
 - Segregation.

Transformation Action Workshop II – Main Results

(month 15)

Local TAWs – Meck-Pomm:

Ambition 2:

- Rewetting it is expected to reduce negative externalities of production.
- Potential of paludiculture, like reed roofs, house insulation or packaging materials is still underdeveloped.
- Little product to upscale production and farmers claim that there is no secure outlet market yet.

Ambition 3:

- Land ownership ≠ land management (e.g., land ownership makes it difficult to assess ex ante who would benefit or be disadvantaged by large-scale rewetting).
- Insecurity regarding income and value of the land.

Transformation Action Workshop II – Main Results

(month 15)

Local TAWs – Meck-Pomm:

Overall thoughts:

- The synthesizing effects of spatial planning and its objective of balancing multiple interests between and within regions is not unfolding its potential.
- According to the lower nature conservation authority, biodiversity protection is not considered sufficiently. Small areas that are part of the larger rewetted areas but are for some reason unsuitable for paludiculture can benefit biodiversity even beyond the general positive effects.
- Education, information and knowledge sharing.
- Adaptation of institutional planning system is needed on several levels.
- Financial incentives are not yet taken up sufficiently – e.g., the financial instrument of CO₂ certificates is still in its infancy and does not work yet on a larger scale.
- Farmers can now also receive direct payments for rewetted areas.
- Need to establish strong networks and ease information access for people newly joining existing networks.
- Measure outside the local and regional system, for example considering the food system, to decrease competition for agricultural land.

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Municipal Spatial Planning

Mafra Municipality, Portugal

Spatial Planning and Management Instruments (WP ₁)	Environmental Assessment Instruments (WP ₂)	Economic and Financial Instruments (WP ₃)
<p>Ecosystem services mapping, analysis, assessment, monitoring.</p> <p>Green infrastructures (strategy?) to go beyond the Portuguese (minimum) legal requirements.</p> <p>Ecosystem services / Green infrastructures: to demonstrate the added value for different economic/social pressures.</p>	<p>Scenarisation with system dynamics.</p> <p>Stakeholders engagement approach.</p> <p>Adoption of an ecosystem services approach.</p>	<p>Inequalities and value of land.</p> <p>Restoration of habitats / Ecosystem services and green infrastructure.</p> <p>Funding schemes.</p> <p>'Fundo Municipal de Sustentabilidade Ambiental e Urbanística' – how to use it as a central funding scheme for biodiversity/ecosystem services valuation within the Municipal Master Plan and how to be effectively implemented?</p>

Compilation of Results – Reflection on the integration of the instruments

Mapping ecosystem services (green infrastructure, green roofs), to be integrated in the master plan or create a specific regulation for that.

It is OK to keep more than one ecosystem service per land use, considering the concept of multifunctional landscapes.

Integrate ecosystem services in legally based planning instruments. Municipal plan can receive the municipal ecological structure and the infrastructure.

Ecosystem services (ES)

The municipal master plan can be a key instrument in integrating ecosystem services into the planning system.

The Municipality needs to provide a strong framework – maybe through the Land Use map.

Zoom in three representative areas (maybe based on the degree of land use intensity).

The Fersina, regenerating an urban river

Trento Municipality, Italy

Spatial Planning and Management Instruments (WP1)	Environmental Assessment Instruments (WP2)	Economic and Financial Instruments (WP3)
<p>1st level intervention: Protocol of Agreed Intervention on multi-scalar administrative levels, between the Comune di Trento and the Provincia Autonoma di Trento (main stakeholders) with other local stakeholders. This is the first step to set up a team to collaborate between offices to reach the requalification goal of the Fersina with a cross-disciplinary and cross-administrative approach.</p> <p>2nd level intervention: Fersina River requalification project</p> <p>3rd level intervention: Integration with Trento planning process</p> <p>Ecosystem services analysis and monitoring</p>	<p>Strategic Environmental Assessment to look into different requalification options and land use options that would enhance biodiversity values</p> <p>Monitoring programme</p>	<p>Simulation / modeling in terms of value property – e.g., Fluvial / urban park</p> <p>Economic revenues of public activities within the river and with public / private entities</p> <p>Land ownership / resistance / real estate market</p> <p>Land property betterment taxes impact fees tools for preventing gentrification</p>

Compilation of Results – Reflection on the integration of the instruments

EAs as decision support tools. Analysis of impacts in most important areas. For prioritising interests and identifying mitigation measures.

Masterplan development based on ecosystem services analysis collaborating with stakeholders and partners.

Environmental Assessment: Involvement of stakeholders in the process enrich the analysis and can be used after decision for implementation (understanding / accepting) the impacts.

Administrative Instruments Revision

Integration of results and approach in current revisions of the planning instruments [Building Regulation and PRG] of the Comune di Trento

Gentrification *mitigation measures*

Pilot projects developments (i.e., Urban Fluvial park hotspots, Canyon Park) - results to be integrated into instruments

Rewetting Peatlands and Reforestation

Mecklenburg-Vorpommern Federal State, Germany

Spatial Planning and Management Instruments (WP ₁)	Environmental Assessment Instruments (WP ₂)	Economic and Financial Instruments (WP ₃)
<p>Land readjustments: reasoning, consolidation, ownership</p> <p>Identification of potential areas for peatland rewetting (with schemes to tackle the challenge of land ownership)</p>	<p>Integration of climate mitigation / adaptation and biodiversity (and synergies) in the Strategic Environmental Assessment</p> <p>Strategic Environmental Assessment policy brief: call attention to the importance of this instrument at different governance levels</p>	<p>Benchmark of existing schemes that could be adjusted / adapted to peatland rewetting (e.g., insurance schemes, public-private partnerships, compensation)</p>

Compilation of Results – Reflection on the integration of the instruments

Use Environmental Impact Assessment and Strategic Environmental Assessment to determine areas where rewetting would be most beneficial in terms of climate change mitigation and other benefits, especially biodiversity.

Causal loop diagram tool, finished in the summer.

Put the extra benefit of Strategic Environmental Assessment process for large scale rewetting for biodiversity protection/ restoration and amenity landscapes into the policy brief.

Use Strategic Environmental Assessment for assessing different pathways (rewetting options that are different in biodiversity protection and other benefits).

Larger scale rewetting also need to generate benefits for biodiversity.

If there are farmers that are more willing to take the risk of rewetting, they could get compensation to swap into the rewetting area.

Land re-assembly

How is it applied in different settings? (Particular the legal setting)

How can it be useful for small scale and large-scale rewetting?

Discussing with Nature park which options for land re-assembly would be possibly useful.

Is Strategic Environmental Assessment and Environmental Impact Assessment applied in land re-assembly?

Who bears the cost of land re-assembly? Is there any compensation for farmers? Is there enough capacity in the federal state to do this?

Using Strategic Environmental Assessment as a communication tool and dialog platform.

Lock-In: resistance against rewetting. Political and societal initiatives needs do influence culture and identity.

Strategic Environmental Assessment (SEA)

Activity 3
Sharing results

Funded by the European union

